

Haematotoxicological and hepatotoxic inductions of a geophagic substance (Calabash chalk) on the albino rat (*Rattus norvegicus*)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated probable effects of a geophagic material - *Calabash chalk* on the haematology and liver enzyme activities of the mammalian model- *Rattus norvegicus*. Twenty four albino rats were acclimatised and exposed to 12.5, 25.0 and 50.0 % (w/w) toxicant-feed mixture. After 2 weeks, the animals were sacrificed and their blood as well as liver enzyme function activities were assessed. The higher toxicant concentrations induced lower body weights in the mammals [$F_{(46|18,5)} > F_{crit(4,30)}$] at $p < 0.05$. Mean maximum white blood cell ($15.0 \pm 8.84 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$), red blood cell ($6.67 \pm 0.03 \times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$) and haemoglobin counts ($13.4 \pm 0.49 \text{g/dl}$) were recorded in the 12.5% toxicant concentration and least counts ($5.2 \pm 1.05 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$, $6.08 \pm 0.57 \times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$ & $11.5 \pm 1.23 \text{g/dl}$ respectively) were recorded in the 50% toxicant concentration. Highest ($85.1 \pm 2.63\%$) and least ($75.7 \pm 2.13\%$) mean lymphocyte counts were recorded in the control and 50.0% toxicant concentrations respectively. In the 25.0% toxicant concentration, the highest monocyte count was $10.5 \pm 1.75\%$ and the least count was $7.0 \pm 0.52\%$ in the control. Highest granulocyte count of 14.2 ± 3.93 was made in the 12.5% toxicant concentration. Highest mean Alkaline phosphatase activity ($240.67 \pm 48.8 \text{U/L}$) was recorded in the 25.0% toxicant concentration, Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) ($278.00 \pm 19.66 \text{U/L}$) in the 25.0% concentration, Alanine aminotransferase ($104.67 \pm 23.92 \text{U/L}$) in the 50.0% toxicant concentrations, and total ($0.31 \pm 0.15 \text{mg/dL}$) and conjugated bilirubins ($0.12 \pm 0.03 \text{mg/dL}$) both in the 12.5% toxicant concentration. The toxicant concentrations induced significant increases in serum AST activity (Sig. $F = 0.02$; $p < 0.05$). Calabash chalk induced slight increases in granulocytes and liver enzyme activities, indicating exposure to systemic distress in the mammal.

Citation: Ogbuagu DH, Nwachukwu IN, Nwazuluahu AC, Kalakiya NP (2017). Haematotoxicological and hepatotoxic inductions of a geophagic substance (Calabash chalk) on the albino rat (*Rattus norvegicus*). *Journal of Environmental Toxicology and Public Health* 2: 14-26. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1010453>

Received September 5, 2017; **Accepted** October 3, 2017; **Published** October 13, 2017.

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Competing Interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Keywords: geophagia, calabash chalk, haematological inductions, liver function enzyme activities, chalk, clay

1. INTRODUCTION

Geophagia has been defined as the practice of eating earth, including soil and chalk [1]. People engage in geophagia for a variety of reasons including religious beliefs, medicinal purposes, or as part of a regular diet [2]. One geophagic material is *Calabash chalk*, which is popularly consumed by members of Nigerian and West African communities for pleasure and by pregnant women as a remedy for morning sickness [3]. *Calabash chalk*, also known as *Calabar stone*, *Poto*, *La craie*, *Argiles*, *Mabele*, *Nzu* and *Ndom* is available in a variety of forms including powder, moulded shapes, and blocks. Though native to Africa, Moses *et al.* [4]

reported that it is also available in the United Kingdom in ethnic stores and markets. The practice of eating *Calabash chalk* has also been observed among women of African descent in the southern United States, especially in Georgia [3]. In addition, *Calabash chalk* is also used in facial masks and soaps [5]. Although this chalk is consumed by both sexes and by many age groups, the prevalence of chalk consumption is greater among women, especially during pregnancy [6].

This chalk is a naturally occurring substance made up of fossilised sea shells but can be prepared artificially [5], using a combination of clay and mud, with other ingredients such as

sand, wood ash and sometimes salt. This mixture is moulded and then heated to produce the final product. The chalk has the same structure as aluminium silicate hydroxide, which is a member of the kaolin clay group with a possible formula $Al_2Si_2O_5(OH)_4$ [7]. Multi-elemental analysis using energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy identified 22 elements in *Calabash chalk*, including lead and aluminium, and persistent organic pollutants [7], even as an earlier report by Campbell and Belfast [8] had established the presence of arsenic in the chalk. Lead and other toxic elements when present in the chalk have been reported to be associated with numerous gastrointestinal disorders including nausea, ulcers, and gastritis [9]. Other studies have shown the availability of even pathogenic organisms such as worm ova in clay that was not processed or obtained in highly hygienic places [10].

Studies on the use of clay have mainly focused on its cultural, nutritional and medicinal utility notwithstanding that craving is usually the most prevalent reason given for its use [11, 12]. Researchers seem not to study the effects of consumption of clay, particularly *Calabash chalk* on mammalian systems functionality, against the fact that its rampant use and disposal could constitute waste in the environment for possible uptake by organisms. The few existing researches on this chalk in our local climate include those of Ekong *et al.* [13] on its effect on femur bone morphometry and mineralization in young Wistar rats, and Akpantah *et al.* [14] on its effects on some haematological parameters in female adult Wistar rats. This paucity has therefore prompted the need for this research on its possible effects on both the haematology and hepatology of a mammal, so as to provide a more comprehensive knowledge of the ecotoxicology of the substance on biotic components of the environment.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Acquisition and acclimatization of test organisms

A total of 24 pure breed albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) of about six weeks old, purchased from the Animal Farm of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka and weighing 189.10 ± 4.35 g were used to in the study. The animals, kept in the Pollution Laboratory of the Department of Environmental Technology, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo State at an average room temperature of $28.0 \pm 0.02^\circ\text{C}$ were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks; with a 12-hour light and 12-hour dark cycle. During acclimatization the animals were fed the Broiler Super Starter Super-Deluxe Animal Feed manufactured by Premiere Feed Mills Co Ltd (a subsidiary of Flour Mill Nig. Plc) and drinking water *ad libitum*. During this period they were randomly divided into four groups and housed in iron cages with perforated roof and side lids, and bedded with

dry wood shavings that were changed daily to prevent maggotry.

2.2 Formulation of toxicant

Calabash chalk blocks were obtained from Ihiagwa Main Market in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria and ground into powder manually. Exactly 122.15, 61.08 and 30.54g of the powder were weighed out and made up to 244.3g toxicant-feed mixtures in each case. This translated to 50.0, 25.0 and 12.5% toxicant concentrations (w/w) in the respective toxicant-feed mixtures. A control formulation containing 100% feed only was also prepared.

2.3. Exposure of test organism, sacrifice and blood sample collection

After 2 weeks of acclimatization, 6 rats were randomly distributed into 4 different cages and labelled CGA, CGB, CGC and CGD (control). Thereafter, the animals were fed the different toxicant concentrations and water *ad libitum* for a further 2 weeks.

After this exposure period, 3 randomly selected rats were weighed with electronic weighing balance from each treatment and control cage. A rat was collected at a time and euthanized with chloroform in a sealed container. Subsequently, 5 ml syringes and 21-gauge needles were used to collect blood samples directly from the heart of the rats through cardiac puncture. The blood samples were immediately transferred into Ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA) coated tube to prevent clotting for haematological counts. The bottles were subsequently inverted severally for homogenization. However, samples for liver enzyme function tests were collected in plain bottles. All samples were properly labelled and taken to the medical laboratory for further analysis.

2.4. Haematological tests

Haematological assessments of White Blood Cells (WBC) counts, Red Blood Cell (RBC) films and haemoglobin concentrations (HGB) were carried out at the Ace Medical Laboratory (AML), Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria according to methods provided by the District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Country National Committee for Clinical Standards, references and selected procedures for the quantitative determination of haemoglobin in blood.

2.4.1. Equipment and detection principles

The H18 LIGHT haematology blood cell counter auto-analyser was used to analyse blood samples. The instrument has 3 part leukocytes sub-population differentiation. Some of the haematological parameters for whole blood specimens that were determined by the analyser include those in Table 1. The detection principle of WBC and RBC is the electrical resistance detection impedancemetry. The instrument counts and sizes the cells by

detecting and measuring changes in electrical resistance when a particle (such as a cell)

passes through a gem aperture sensor.

Table 1. Haematological parameters for whole blood specimens measured by the H18 LIGHT Auto-analyser

Items	Abbreviation	Units
White blood cells	WBC	$10^3/\mu\text{L}$
Lymphocyte percent	LYM%	%
Monocyte percent	MON%	%
Granulocyte percent	GRAN%	%
Red blood cell	RBC	$10^6/\mu\text{L}$
Haemoglobin concentration	HGB	g/dL
Haematocrit	HCT	%
Mean Cell Volume	MCV	fL
Mean Cell Haemoglobin	MCH	Pg
Mean Cell Haemoglobin Concentration	MCHC	g/dL
Platelet	PLT	$10^3/\mu\text{L}$

For the detection principle of haemoglobin, adding lyse to the blood sample will crack the membrane of red blood cells promptly and transfer it into a kind of compound which can absorb the wavelength of 540nm. Absorbance background is performed with diluents, and measurement of the optical density of the sample allows circulation of the haemoglobin concentration.

For red blood cell volume, amplitude of the pulses is correlated to the sizes of the RBC. The instrument measures each cell and classifies it according to its volume by a pre-set classification program as follows:

120-1000 fL = WBC, 82-98fL = RBC and 2-35fL = PLT

According to the volume, leucocytes handled by lyse can be subdivided into three categories: lymphocytes (LYM), Monocyte (MON), and Granulocyte (GRAN) as follows:

35-90fL = LYM, 90-160fL = MON and 160-450 fL= GRAN

2.4.2. Analytical procedure

Sample was diluted in a conductive liquid since blood cells are bad conductors. This was to ensure that each time a blood cell passes through the aperture, a resistant signal will be generated. When cell goes through the aperture, the resistance is increased as cell volume increases according to Ohm formular:

U=RI, where U =Voltage, I = Current, and R = Resistance.

If "I" is invariable, U is increased as cell volume increases.

The circuit was magnified, the voltage signal was amplified, background noise was removed and signal was received for analysis.

WBC and RBC/PLT were analysed by two different circuits. The Micro Processor Unit analysed and calculated the cells, and further gave the histograms. The count of PLT adopted an advanced liquid, electron and soft system, which can settle the repetitive count of the cells. If RBC centres the analysis area, they will have similar pulses with PLT, which may cause confusion as repetitive count.

However, WBC and RBC were read off the metre and recorded in $10^3/\mu\text{L}$ and $10^6/\mu\text{L}$ respectively.

MCV was determined by measuring the average volume of individual erythrocytes. This number was multiplied by a coincidence correction factor and a calibration factor. The reported value expresses MCV in femtolitres.

2.5. Liver function tests

2.5.1. Determination of aspartate amino transferase (AST) activity

The quantitative determination of AST was carried out in accordance with International Federation of Clinical Chemistry (IFCC) assays procedures.

Principle:

In the presence of α -ketoglutarate, AST in the sample transforms aspartate into oxaloacetate and glutamate. In the presence of NADH and malate dehydrogenate, oxaloacetate is converted into malate nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD). Consuming of NADH per unit time, measured at 340nm, is proportional to the concentration of AST in the sample. The equation of reaction is shown below:

AST reagent kits:

The AST Reagents A and B kits were used. Reagent A kit was 40/80mL by volume and was composed of 80mmol/L Tris buffer with pH of 7.8, 200mmol/L L-aspartate, 600U/L lactate dehydrogenase, and 400U/L malate dehydrogenase.

AST Reagent B kit was 10/40/80mL by volume and was composed of 0.18mmol/L NADH and 12mmol/L α -ketoglutarate.

Analytical procedure:

The Reagents were brought to room temperature (15-25°C). Exactly 800 μ L of Reagent A and 200 μ L of Reagent B were mixed. After 30 seconds, 100 μ L of sample (serum) was added and mixed. The resultant mixture was incubated at 37°C for 1 minute and the initial absorbance of sample read against distilled water at 340nm wavelength, 1cm lightpath and 37°C temperature. Three readings were taken at intervals of 60 seconds and the average value of the absorbance variations per minute calculated to obtain a change in

absorbance per minute ($\Delta A/\text{min}$). AST activity in units/liter was calculated by multiplying $\Delta A/\text{min}$ by a factor, thus:

$$\text{AST Activity (U/L)} = \Delta A/\text{min} * 1636$$

where: 1636 is a factor obtained from Clinical Chemistry Calibrator; Factor was verified using Clinical Chemistry Calibrator to ascertain its correctness for test system before being used.

2.5.2. Determination of Alanine amino transferase (ALT) Activity

The quantitative determination of ALT was carried out in accordance with IFCC regulations.

Principle:

In the presence of α -ketoglutarate, alanine is transformed into pyruvate and glutamate by ALT in the sample. In presence of NADH and lactate dehydrogenase, pyruvate is converted into lactate and NAD. NADH oxidation in time unit measured at 340nm is proportional to ALT concentration in the sample:

ALT reagent kits:

The ALT Reagent A kit was 40/80mL by volume and was composed of 100mmol/L Tris buffer with pH of 7.8, 500mmol/L L-alanine, 100mmol/L lactate dehydrogenase.

ALT Reagent B kit was 10/40/80mL by volume and was composed of 0.18mmol/L NADH, 15mmol/L α -ketoglutarate.

Analytical procedure:

The Reagents A and B were brought to room temperature, (15-25°C). Exactly 800 μ L of Reagent A and 100 μ L of sample (serum) were pipetted into a labeled test tube and mixed. After 30 seconds, 200 μ L of Reagent B was added and contents were mixed. The resultant mixture was incubated at 37°C for 1minute and initial absorbance read against distilled water at 340nm wavelength, 1cm lightpath and at a temperature of 37°C. Three readings were made at time intervals of 60 seconds and average value of absorbance variations per

minute was calculated and $\Delta A/\text{min}$ obtained. ALT activity was derived by multiplying the $\Delta A/\text{min}$ by a factor, thus:

$$\text{ALT Activity (U/L)} = \Delta A/\text{min} * 1672$$

where: 1672 is a factor obtained from Clinical Chemistry Calibrator. Factor was verified for test system using Clinical Chemistry Calibrator before use.

2.5.3. Determination of Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) Activity

The quantitative determination of ALP in blood was done *in vitro* according to DGKC-SCE (German Society for Clinical Chemistry and Scandinavian Society of Clinical Chemistry) specifications.

Principle:

The principle is based on the kinetic determination of ALP according to the following reaction:

ALP Reagents Composition:

ALP Reagents 1 and 2 were used. Reagent 1 was composed of 125mmol/L diethanolamine buffer with pH of 10.2 and 0.625mmol/L magnesium chloride, while Reagent 2 was

composed of 50mmol/L P-nitrophenyl phosphate.

Analytical Procedure:

Exactly 4 volumes of Reagent 1 were mixed with 1 volume of Reagent 2, to obtain the

Working Reagent, and brought to room temperature (15-25°C). Exactly 1000µL of the working reagent and 20µL of serum were pipetted and thoroughly mixed. The resultant mixture was incubated at 37°C for 1 minute and initial absorbance was read against distilled water at 405nm wavelength, 1cm lightpath, and 37°C temperature. Three readings were taken at delay time of 60 seconds. Change in absorbance per minute ($\Delta OD/min$) was measured by calculating the average value of absorbance variations per minute. ALP activity was determined by multiplying $\Delta OD/min$ by a factor, thus:

$$\text{ALP Activity (U/L)} = \Delta OD/min * 2750$$

where: 2750 is a factor obtained from Clinical Chemistry Calibrator.

Factor was verified for correctness using Clinical Chemistry Calibrator.

2.5.4. Determination of total and conjugated (direct) bilirubin levels

Principle:

The quantitative *in vitro* determination of total and direct bilirubin in plasma was done using the calorimetric method based on descriptions by Jendrassik and Grof [15]. Direct (conjugated) bilirubin reacts with diazotized sulphanilic acid in alkaline medium to form a blue-coloured complex. Total bilirubin is determined in the presence of caffeine, which releases albumin-bound bilirubin, by the reaction with diazotized sulphanilic acid.

Reagents composition:

The reagents required in these tests were labeled R1-R4. Reagent 1 (R1) was composed of 29mmol/L sulphanilic acid and 0.17N hydrochloric acid. Reagent 2 (R2) was 38.5mmol/L sodium nitrate. Reagent 3 (R3) was composed of 0.26mol/L caffeine and 0.52mol/L sodium benzoate, while Reagent 4 (R4) constituted of 0.93mol/L tartrate and 1.9N sodium hydroxide. All reagents were ready to use at 15-25°C.

Analytical Procedures:

1. Total bilirubin:

Exactly 200µL R1, 50µL (1 drop) R2, 1000µL R3 and 200µL serum sample were mixed and allowed to stand for 10 minutes at 20-25°C. After, 1000µL R4 was added, mixed, and allowed to stand for 5-30 minutes at 20-25°C. The absorbance of sample was then read against the sample blank (A_{TB}) at 578nm (560-600nm) wavelength, 1cm lightpath and at a reaction temperature of 20-25°C. Total bilirubin levels were calculated thus:

$$\text{Total bilirubin } (\mu\text{mol/L}) = 185 \times A_{TB} (578\text{nm})$$

Or

$$\text{Total bilirubin (mg/dL)} = 10.8 \times A_{TB} (578\text{nm})$$

2. Conjugated bilirubin:

Exactly 200µL R1, 50µL (1 drop) R2, 0.9% sodium chloride (NaCl) and 200µL sample (serum) were mixed and allowed to stand for 10 minutes at 20-25°C. After, the absorbance of the sample was read against the sample blank (A_{DB}) at 546nm wavelength, 1cm lightpath and at a reaction temperature of 20-25°C. Conjugated bilirubin levels were calculated thus:

$$\text{Conjugated bilirubin } (\mu\text{mol/L}) = 246 \times A_{DB} (546\text{nm})$$

Or

$$\text{Conjugated bilirubin (mol/dL)} = 14.4 \times A_{DB} (546\text{nm})$$

2.6. Statistical analysis

The SPSS V. 22.0 and MS Excel® 2007 statistical softwares were used to analyse data. Variation plots were used to represent mean counts of the blood parameters and liver enzyme activity levels. The One-Way ANOVA was used to determine homogeneity in mean variance of haematological counts and hepatological activities, while post-hoc Duncan Multiple Range Test was used to separate means of the parameters at the 95% confidence interval.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effects of toxicant on weight of organisms

The weights of the animals in different concentrations of the toxicant after two weeks exposure period are shown in Table 2. The highest mean weight of 262.91±4.09g was recorded for the animals in the control cage while the least mean weight of 237.34±5.38g was recorded for the animals in CGB (25.0% toxicant concentration). However, the mean weight of the animals in CGA (50.0% toxicant concentration) was 238.85±1.15g, while the mean weight of animals in CGC (12.5% toxicant concentration) was 252.84±4.0g.

The test of homogeneity in mean variance revealed that the different concentrations of the toxicant induced significantly lower weights on the organisms [$F_{(46|18.5)} > F_{crit(4.30)}$] at $P < 0.05$.

3.2 Haematological inductions

The haematological counts and estimations made in the rats after 2 weeks exposure period are shown in Table 3. The highest White Blood Cell (WBC) counts ($32.6 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) was recorded in the CGC1 replicate of the 12.5% toxicant concentration, while the least WBC count ($2.5 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) was recorded in the CGA2 replicate of the 50.0% toxicant concentration. The most and least lymphocyte counts of 90.8% and 65.5% were recorded in the CGD3 control and CGB1 replicate of the 25.0% toxicant concentrations respectively.

Table 2. Weight of albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) exposed to different concentrations of *Calabash chalk* in 244.3g toxicant-feed mixture (w/w) after 2 weeks.

Treatment (% toxicant concentration)	Weight (g)			
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3	Mean weight ± SE
CGA (50.0%)	241.15	237.85	237.55	238.85±1.15
CGB (25.0%)	248.04	230.94	233.04	237.34±5.38
CGC (12.5%)	260.84	248.94	248.74	252.84±4.00
CGD (0.0%)	256.21	262.21	270.31	262.91±4.09

Highest monocyte (14.0%) and granulocyte (20.8%) counts were recorded in the CGB1 replicate of the 25.0% and CGC1 replicate of the 12.5% toxicant concentrations, while the least count of 6.0% and 3.6% were all recorded in the CGD3 replicates of the control concentration. Highest and least Red Blood Cell (RBC) (7.48 & $4.67 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$) and Haemoglobin (HGB) counts (14.5 & 8.5 g/dL) were recorded in the CGA3 and CGA2 replicates of the 50.0% toxicant concentration respectively, while those of Haematocrits (HCT) (43.7% & 29.0%) were recorded in the CGB1 replicate of the 25.0% and CGA2 replicate of the 50.0% toxicant concentrations respectively.

However, Mean Cell Volume (MCV), Mean Cell Haemoglobin (MCH) and Mean Cell Haemoglobin concentrations (MCHC) peaked as 62.5fl in the CGD3 replicate of the control, 21.4pg in the CGC1 replicate of the 12.5% toxicant concentration and 35.9g/dL in the CGC1 replicate of the 12.5% toxicant concentrations respectively. The least counts of the respective haematological variables of 57.6fl, 17.4pg and 29.3g/dL were recorded in the CGB2 replicate of the 25.0% toxicant concentration, and the CGA2 replicate of the 50.0% toxicant concentration (MCH & MCHC). The most counts of platelets (PLT) ($660 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) were recorded in the CGC3 replicate of the 25.0% toxicant concentration and least count ($133 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) was recorded in the CGD3 replicate of the 25.0% toxicant concentration.

Summarily, in the 50.0% toxicant concentration, mean WBC count was $5.2 \pm 1.05 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, RBC was $6.10 \pm 0.57 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ and HGB was 11.7 ± 1.23 g/dL (Fig. 1). In the 25.0% toxicant concentration, mean WBC count was $5.6 \pm 0.96 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, RBC was $6.52 \pm 0.59 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ and HGB was 12.6 ± 1.42 g/dL. Mean WBC count was $15.0 \pm 8.84 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, RBC was $6.67 \pm 0.03 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ and HGB was 13.4 ± 0.49 g/dL in the 12.5% toxicant concentration. However in the control concentration, mean WBC count was $7.5 \pm 0.35 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, RBC $6.64 \pm 0.24 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ and HGB 12.9 ± 0.50 g/dL (Fig. 1).

In the 50% toxicant concentration, mean LYM count was $78.7 \pm 2.13\%$, MON $9.4 \pm 1.19\%$,

GRAN $11.9 \pm 1.21\%$ and HCT $36.2 \pm 2.79\%$, and in the 25% toxicant concentration, mean LYM count was $75.8 \pm 5.43\%$, MON $10.5 \pm 1.75\%$, GRAN $13.7 \pm 3.74\%$ and HCT 39.0 ± 4.13 . Mean LYM count was $76.2 \pm 4.45\%$, MON $9.5 \pm 0.57\%$, GRAN $14.2 \pm 3.93\%$ and HCT $40.0 \pm 0.59\%$ in the 12.5% toxicant concentration, while in the control setup, mean LYM count was $85.1 \pm 2.63\%$, MON $7.0 \pm 0.52\%$, GRAN $7.8 \pm 2.12\%$ and HCT $39.6 \pm 1.99\%$ (Fig. 2).

In the 50% toxicant concentration, mean PLT was $203 \pm 21.18 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, MCHC 31.9 ± 0.98 g/dL, MCH 18.7 ± 0.46 pg and MCV 58.9 ± 0.28 fl, and in the 25.0% toxicant concentration, mean PLT of $316.7 \pm 75.17 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, MCHC of 32.3 ± 0.50 g/dL, MCH of 19.2 ± 3.47 pg and MCV of 59.8 ± 1.27 fl were recorded. Mean PLT was $379 \pm 140.50 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, MCHC was 33.5 ± 1.22 g/dL, MCH was 20.03 ± 0.71 pg and MCV was 601 ± 0.59 fl in the 12.5% toxicant concentration. However in the control concentration, mean PLT was $230.7 \pm 70.26 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, MCHC was 32.6 ± 0.44 g/dL, MCH was 19.4 ± 0.22 pg, and MCV was 59.6 ± 1.48 fl (Fig. 3).

WBC counts of 5.5, 2.5, and $7.6 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ were made in the CGA1, CGA2 and CGA3 replicates of the 50.0% toxicant concentration, while RBC counts were 6.16, 4.67 and $7.48 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ in the CGA replicates. However, 12.0, 8.5 and 14.5 g/dl of HGB, 84.6, 76.6 and 74.8 % of LYM, 6.2, 11.9 and 10.1 % of MON, 9.2, 11.5 and 15.1 % of GRAN, 37.0, 29.0 and 42.6 % of HCT, 60.1, 59.6 and 57.0 fl of MCV, 19.4, 17.4 and 19.3 pg of MCH, 32.4, 29.3 and 34.0 g/dL MCHC and 145, 219 and $245 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ of PLT were also recorded in the CGA1, CGA2 and CGA3 of the 50% toxicant concentration respectively (Table 3). In the 25.0% toxicant concentration, 4.9, 4.4 and $7.5 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ of WBC, 7.06, 5.35 and $7.15 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ of RBC and 13.9, 9.8 and 14.2 g/dl of HGB were counted in the CGB1, CGB2 and CGB3 replicates. However, 65.5, 78.1 and 83.9 % LYM, 14.0, 8.9 and 8.6 % MON, 20.5, 13.0 and 7.6 % GRAN, 43.7, 30.8 and 42.6 % HCT, 62.0, 57.6 and 59.7 fl MCV, 19.6, 18.3 and 19.8 pg MCH, 31.8, 31.8 and 33.3 g/dl MCHC and 466, 227 and $257 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ PLT were also counted in the replicate concentrations (Table 3).

Table 3. Haematological parameters of the albino rats – *R. norvegicus* exposed to different concentrations of calabash chalk after 2 weeks.

Treatments (% concentration in 244.3g of feed)	Replicates	WBC (10 ³ /μl)	RBC (10 ⁶ /μl)	HGB (g/dl)	LYM (%)	MON (%)	GRAN (%)	HCT (%)	MCV (fl)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g/dl)	PLT (10 ³ /ul)
CGA (50.0%)	A1	5.50	6.16	12.00	84.60	6.20	9.20	37.00	60.10	19.40	32.40	145.00
	A2	2.50	4.67	8.50	76.60	11.90	11.50	29.00	59.60	17.40	29.30	219.00
	A3	7.60	7.48	14.50	74.80	10.10	15.10	42.60	57.00	19.30	34.00	245.00
	Mean±SE	5.20±1.05	6.10±0.57	11.67±1.23	78.67±2.13	9.40±1.19	11.93±1.21	36.20±2.79	58.90±0.68	18.70±0.46	31.90±0.98	203±21.18
CGB (25.5%)	B1	4.90	7.06	13.90	65.50	14.00	20.50	43.70	62.00	19.60	31.80	466.00
	B2	4.40	5.35	9.80	78.10	8.90	13.00	30.80	57.60	18.30	31.80	227.00
	B3	7.50	7.15	14.20	83.90	8.60	7.60	42.60	59.70	19.80	33.30	257.00
	Mean±SE	5.60±0.96	6.52±0.59	12.63±1.42	75.83±5.43	10.50±1.75	13.70±3.74	39.03±4.13	59.77±1.27	19.23±0.47	32.30±0.50	316.67±75.15
CGC (12.5%)	C1	32.60	6.67	14.30	69.10	10.10	20.80	39.80	59.80	21.40	35.90	238.00
	C2	7.70	6.61	12.60	75.20	10.10	14.70	39.10	59.20	19.00	32.20	239.00
	C3	4.70	6.73	13.30	84.40	8.40	7.20	41.10	61.20	19.70	32.30	660.00
	Mean±SE	15.00±8.84	6.67±0.03	13.40±0.49	76.23±4.45	9.53±0.57	14.23±3.93	40.00±0.59	60.07±0.59	20.03±0.71	33.47±1.22	379±140.50
CGD (0.0%)	D1	7.40	6.19	11.90	82.50	7.40	10.10	35.70	57.70	19.20	33.30	192.00
	D2	8.20	7.00	13.40	82.50	7.70	9.80	40.90	58.50	19.10	32.70	367.00
	D3	7.00	6.75	13.40	90.40	6.00	3.60	42.20	62.50	19.80	31.80	133.00
	Mean±SE	7.53±0.35	6.65±0.24	12.90±0.50	85.13±2.63	7.03±0.52	7.83±2.12	39.60±1.99	59.57±1.48	19.37±0.22	32.60±0.44	230.67±70.26

WBC=White Blood Cells, RBC=Red Blood Cells, HGB=Haemoglobin, LYM=lymphocytes, MON=Monocytes, GRAN=Granulocytes, HCT=Haematocrits, MCV=Mean Cell Volume, MCH=Mean Cell Haemoglobin, MCHC=Mean Cell Haemoglobin Concentration, PLT=Platelets

The 12.5% toxicant concentration resulted to 32.6, 7.7 and 4.7 $\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ WBC, 6.52, 6.67 and 6.61 $\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ RBC, and 14.3, 12.6 and 13.3 g/dl HGB counts in the CGC1, CGC2 and CGC3 replicates treatments. However, 69.1, 75.2 and 84.4 % LYM, 10.1, 10.1 and 8.4 % MON, 20.8, 14.7 and 7.2 % GRAN, 39.8, 39.1 and 41.1 % HCT, 59.8, 59.2 and 61.2 fl MCV, 21.4, 19.0 and 19.7 pg MCH, 35.9, 32.2 and 32.3 g/dl MCHC and 238, 239 and 660 $\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ PLT were recorded in the CGC1, CGC2 and CGC3 replicates of the 12.5% toxicant concentration respectively (Table 3). In the control, 7.4, 8.2 and 7.0 $\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ WBC, 6.19, 7.00 and 6.75 $\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$ RBC, and 11.9, 13.4 and 13.4 g/dl HGB were counted in replicates of the CGD treatment. However, 82.5, 82.5 and 90.4 % of LYM, 7.4, 7.7 and 6.0 % of MON, 10.1, 9.8 and 3.6 % of GRAN, 35.7, 40.9 and 42.2 % of HCT, 57.7, 58.5 and 62.5 fl of MCV, 19.2, 19.1 and 19.8 pg of MCH, 33.3, 32.7 and 31.8 g/dl of MCHC and 192, 367 and 133 $\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ PLT were also counted in respective CGD replicates of the control treatment (Table 3).

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) test revealed that the different concentrations of toxicant caused no significant inductions on the haematological variables of the mammals (Sig. F values= 0.433 WBC, 0.852 RBC, 0.768 HGB, 0.393 LYM, 0.329 MON, 0.477 GRAN, 0.811 HCT, 0.899 MCV, 0.440 MCH, 0.716 MCHC and 0.513 PLT). However, the pair-wise Student's t-test comparison in haematological inductions between the toxicant treatments and control showed high significant Pearson correlations (Sig r = 0.000 each) at the 95% confidence limit.

3.3 Hepatological inductions

The levels of liver function enzymes in the rats after 2 weeks exposure period are shown in Table 4. The highest level of Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) activity (314U/L) was recorded in the CGB3 replicate of the 25.0% toxicant concentration, while the least activity of 10U/L was recorded in the CGA1 replicate of the 50.0% toxicant concentration. The order of ALP activity in the replicates was CGB3(314U/L) > CGB2(260U/L) > CGA3(236U/L) > CGC3(177U/L) > CGB(148U/L) > CGC2(110U/L) > CGD1(69U/L) > CGD2(65U/L) > CGD3(62U/L) > CGA2(44U/L) > CGC1(13U/L) > CGA1(10U/L). The highest Aspartate amino transferase (AST) activity (280U/L) was recorded in the CGB3 replicate of the 25.0% toxicant concentration, while the least level of activity (10U/L) was recorded in the CGD3 replicate of the control treatment. The order of AST activity in the replicates was CGB3(311U/L) > CGB2(280U/L) > CGB1(243U/L) > CGA2(241U/L) > CGA3(221U/L) > CGD1(170U/L) > CGD2(165U/L) > CGA1(155U/L) > CGC3(147U/L) > CGC2(120U/L) > CGC1(83U/L) > CGD3(10U/L).

For Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) activity, highest activity of 132U/L was recorded in the CGA1 replicate of the 50.0% toxicant concentration, while the least activity (50U/L) was recorded in the CGD3 replicate of the control treatment. The order of ALT activity in the replicates was CGA1(132U/L) > CGA2(125U/L) > CGC3(120U/L) > CGC2(110U/L) > CGD1(101U/L) > CGD2(98U/L) > CGB3(82U/L) > CGB2(78U/L) > CGB1(73U/L) > CGC1(69U/L) > CGA3(57U/L) > CGD3(50U/L). The highest level of Total bilirubin (0.60mg/dL) was recorded in the CGC1 replicate of the 12.5% toxicant concentration, while the least level of 0.10mg/dL was recorded in the CGA3, CGB3, CGC3, and CGD3 replicates of the 50.0, 25.0, 12.5%, and control treatments respectively.

The order of total bilirubin in the replicates was CGC1(0.60mg/dL) > CGB1(0.50mg/dL) > CGA1(0.40mg/dL) > CGB2/CGA2(0.30mg/dL) > CGC2(0.23mg/dL) > CGD1(0.20mg/dL) > CGD2(0.15mg/dL) > CGD3/CGC3/CGB3/CGA3(0.10mg/dL). Highest conjugated bilirubin level of 0.18mg/dL was recorded in the CGC1 replicate of the 12.5% toxicant concentration, while the CGD2 replicate of the control treatment recorded the least level of 0.04mg/dL. The order of conjugated bilirubin levels in the replicates was CGC1(0.18mg/dL) > CGB1/CGB2(0.13mg/dL) > CGA1(0.11mg/dL) > CGC2/CGD1(0.10mg/dL) > CGA2(0.09mg/dL) > CGC3/CGB3(0.08mg/dL) > CGA3(0.07mg/dL) > CGD3(0.05mg/dL) > CGD2(0.04mg/dL).

Summarily, mean peak ALP activity (240.67 \pm 48.8U/L) was recorded in the 25.0% (CGB) toxicant concentration, while the least mean activity level (65.33 \pm 1.43U/L) was recorded in the control treatment (CGD) (Fig 4). The highest mean AST (278.00 \pm 19.66U/L) and ALT (104.67 \pm 23.92U/L) activities were recorded in the 25.0 (CGB) and 50.0 % (CGA) toxicant concentrations, while their least mean values (115.00 \pm 37.14 and 77.67 \pm 2.60U/L) were recorded in the control and 25.0% toxicant concentrations respectively. The highest mean levels of total bilirubin (0.31 \pm 0.15mg/dL) and conjugated bilirubin (0.12 \pm 0.03mg/dL) were recorded in the 12.5%(CGC) toxicant concentration, while the least mean levels of 0.15 \pm 0.02 and 0.06 \pm 0.01mg/dL were recorded in the control treatment (Fig 4). The ANOVA test revealed that the different concentrations of the toxicant caused significant inductions on the levels of AST activity (Sig=0.020) at p<0.05only.

A Post-hoc mean separation using Duncan Multiple Range Test revealed that the toxicant actually induced significantly different ALP and AST activities between the 25.0% toxicant concentration and control treatment, and in AST between the 25.0, 12.5% and control concentrations (Table 5).

Table 4. Levels of liver function enzymes in the albino rat *R. norvegicus* exposed to graded concentrations of calabash chalk after 2 weeks.

Treatment (%toxicant concentrations in 244.3g of feed)	Replicate	ALP (U/L)	AST (U/L)	ALT (U/L)	Total bilirubin (mg/dL)	Conjugated Bilirubin (mg/dL)
CGD (0.0%)	CGD1	69	170	101	0.20	0.10
	CGD2	65	165	98	0.15	0.04
	CGD3	62	10	50	0.10	0.05
	Mean±SE	(\bar{X} = 65.33±1.43)	(\bar{X} = 115.00±37.14)	(\bar{X} = 83.00±11.68)	(\bar{X} = 0.15±0.02)	(\bar{X} = 0.06±0.01)
CGC (12.5%)	CGC1	13	83	69	0.60	0.18
	CGC2	110	120	110	0.23	0.10
	CGC3	177	147	120	0.10	0.08
	Mean±SE	(\bar{X} = 100.00±47.61)	(\bar{X} = 116.67±18.55)	(\bar{X} = 99.67±15.60)	(\bar{X} = 0.31±0.15)	(\bar{X} = 0.12±0.03)
CGB (25.0%)	CGB1	148	243	73	0.50	0.13
	CGB2	260	280	78	0.30	0.13
	CGB3	314	311	82	0.10	0.08
	Mean±SE	(\bar{X} = 240.67±48.89)	(\bar{X} = 278.00±19.66)	(\bar{X} = 77.67±2.60)	(\bar{X} = 0.30±0.12)	(\bar{X} = 0.11±0.02)
CGA (50.0%)	CGA1	10	155	132	0.40	0.11
	CGA2	44	241	125	0.30	0.09
	CGA3	236	221	57	0.10	0.07
	Mean±SE	(\bar{X} = 96.67±70.35)	(\bar{X} = 205.67±25.98)	(\bar{X} = 104.67±23.92)	(\bar{X} = 0.27±0.09)	(\bar{X} = 0.09±0.01)

ALP=Alkaline Phosphatase, AST=Aspartate aminotransferase, ALT=Alanine aminotransferase

Table 5. Mean separation in levels of liver function enzymes in the albino rat (*R. norvegicus*) exposed to graded concentrations of *Calabash chalk* after 2 weeks using Duncan Multiple Range test ($p < 0.05$).

Liver function enzymes	Toxicant concentrations			
	50.0%	25.0%	12.5%	0.0%
ALP	96.667 ^{ab}	240.667 ^a	100.000 ^{ab}	65.333 ^b
AST	205.667 ^{ab}	278.000 ^a	116.667 ^b	115.000 ^b
ALT	104.667 ^a	76.667 ^a	99.667 ^a	83.000 ^a
Total Bilirubin	0.267 ^a	0.300 ^a	0.371 ^a	0.150 ^a
Conjugated Bilirubin	0.090 ^a	0.113 ^a	0.113 ^a	0.063 ^a

Values of liver function enzymes with same superscript are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$. ALP=Alkaline phosphatase, AST=Aspartate amino transferase, ALT=Alanine amino transferase

4. DISCUSSION

Alimba *et al.* [16] had observed that one among the validated method for investigating the immuno-toxic potentials for chemicals, primarily in rodents is change in cellular components of blood, especially in the white blood cell counts. Results from the current work indicate that the different toxicant concentrations induced significant weight losses in the organisms after two weeks exposure period. Usually, weight is a vital sign of health status of organisms. Chevrier *et al.* [17] commented that although there appear to be a consensus among scientists and clinicians that body weight loss reduces the risk of several chronic diseases, these apparently favourable effects should be balanced against any potentially harmful side effects of weight loss. This was a backdrop from their observation in obese subjects that weight loss produced an increase in blood concentration of potentially toxic organochlorine pollutants in animals that can cause plasma and subcutaneous adipose tissue concentrations of the pollutants they studied.

Results from the current study also revealed a high increase in the mean white blood cell counts in the 12.5% toxicant concentration and a decrease in the higher 25.0 and 50.0 %

toxicant concentrations, as well as lower lymphocyte counts in blood samples exposed to the treatments with reference to the control set up. These observations indicate some degrees of impairment on the immune system of the mammals. Alimba *et al.* [16] asserts that recognition that xenobiotic can impair the function of the immune system has led to the development and validation of variety of methods in immuno-toxicology. White blood cells are important part of the body's defence against infections and foreign substances [18].

Comparable haematocrit, mean cell volume, mean cell haemoglobin, red blood cells, haemoglobin counts and mean cell haemoglobin counts were recorded in mammals exposed to the toxicant. A slight increase was observed in the monocyte and granulocyte counts of the animals exposed to the treatments, while varying counts of platelets were also recorded. This differs from observations made by Alimba *et al.* [16] in rats exposed to municipal solid waste leachate, Svobodova *et al.* [19] in freshwater carp and rainbow trouts exposed to copper, and Nunia *et al.* [20] in Swiss albino mice exposed to gamma irradiation by diatazem. Significant decreases in these and other differential counts reflect decreases in antibody production, which could make the

animal vulnerable to antigens from parasites, pathogens and even toxicants. This could also reflect less stress induction by the toxicant, leading to less immunological reaction to produce more antibodies to combat antigens. Similar reports in Perch dwelling in natural water bodies polluted with a mixture of heavy metals (Zn, Cu, Pb, Cd and Hg) has been made by Larsson *et al.* [21], and that in humans occupationally exposed to 10ppm concentration of benzene had since also been made by Chang [22].

This study also revealed other inductions, such as numerical increases in Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Aspartate amino transferase (AST), and Alanine amino transferase (ALT) activities (except in the 25.0% toxicant concentration), total bilirubin and conjugated bilirubin levels by the toxicant concentrations. It is reported that increased levels of these liver function parameters in blood could indicate liver distress/diseases [23]. Elevated blood ALP is one of the signs of space-occupying lesions in the liver, and could be indicative of liver tumour development [24, 25]. Rosalki and McIntyre [24] had observed that mild ALP increases may be evident in cirrhosis and hepatitis of congestive cardiac failures.

AST and ALT are identified as serum markers of liver integrity and been associated with liver parenchyma cells, could at elevated levels, be indicative of liver parenchymal damage [26, 27]. Furthermore, heightened levels of these biomarkers have been implicated in hepatocellular necrosis, membrane damage or loss of functional integrity of cellular membrane in liver [28, 29]. According to Marshall [30] and AACC [31], ALT levels often vary between normal and slightly increased in chronic hepatitis. AACC [31] also opined that other causes of moderate increase in ALT could include obstruction of bile ducts, cirrhosis (usually the result of chronic hepatitis or bile duct obstruction), and tumours in the liver.

Regarding the mild increases in Total and Conjugated Bilirubin levels in this study, Dahiru and Obidoa [32] observed that an elevated level of total bilirubin reflects depth of jaundice and can indicate a number of problems such as haemolytic anaemia, internal haemorrhage, cirrhosis, and viral hepatitis. It is stated that no conjugated bilirubin is present in blood under normal conditions and that the incidence of its increased blood levels may be linked to hepatitis and space-occupying- and obstructive-lesions, such as carcinoma of the head of the pancreas, common bile duct or ampulla of Vater [31, 33, 34].

5. CONCLUSION

This research showed that *Calabash chalk* caused mild degrees of blood cells immune-defence inductions in the mammal- *Rattus norvegicus*, even though the organisms lost

significant weight when they were exposed to the toxicant. However, there were significant increases in serum Aspartate transaminase and Alkaline phosphatase activities, as well as slight increases in serum Alanine transaminase activity, and Total- and Conjugated-Bilirubin levels in the mammal.

Calabash chalk induced mild haematotoxicity and hepatotoxicity in the albino rat- *Rattus norvegicus*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We appreciate the managers of the Animal Farm of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka for providing us with the experimental animals used in this research. We also thank the Ace Medical Laboratory (AML), Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria for the laboratory analysis. Worthy of mention is the assistance given by Dr. Cosmos O. Ujowundu of the Department of Biochemistry, Federal University of Technology, Owerri in certain procedures and supply of the cages used in the research.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

DHO designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. INN managed the analyses and assisted in writing the protocol of the study. ACN and NPK managed the literature searches as well as assisted in the analyses of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed. All experiments have been examined and approved by the ethics committee of the Departments of Environmental Technology (EVT), Microbiology (MCB) and Biochemistry (BCH) of the Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.

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